
Spectrophotometric Determination of Daclatasvir Dihydrochloride by Ion-Pair Reaction with Bromophenol Blue, Bromothymol Blue and Bromocresol Green

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Abstract Simple, rapid, cost-effective, sensitive spectrophotometric methods were developed for the determination of antiviral C drug (Daclatasvir dihydrochloride) in pure and dosage forms. The methods are based on the formation of ion-pair complexes between the drug and acid dyes (*i.e.*, Bromothymol blue (BTB), bromocresol green (BCG) and bromophenol blue (BPB) solutions. The formed complexes were measured at 420, 416 and 415 nm for BCG, BPB and BTB methods, respectively, against a similarly prepared blank reagent. The analytical parameters and their effects on the reported systems were investigated. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration ranges of 5.0 - 60.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, 5.0 - 70.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 5.0 - 60.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for BCG, BTB and BPB methods, respectively. The composition of the ion pairs was determined to be 1:2 for DCT with BCG, BTB and BPB. The molar absorptivity, Sandell sensitivity, limits of detection and limits of quantification were calculated. Other method validation parameters, such as precision, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness and selectivity, were satisfactory. The accuracy and validity of the method were established by recovery studies via standard addition technique. The proposed methods have been successfully applied for the analysis of the studied drug in their pure and dosage form. Statistical comparison of the results with the HPLC method indicated excellent agreement and no significant difference in accuracy and precision.

Keywords spectrophotometry, ion-pair complex, daclatasvir, bromophenol blue, bromocresol green, Bromothymol blue

Introduction

Hepatitis C is a liver disease produced by the hepatitis C virus (HCV) and can cause liver cirrhosis, liver failure, liver cancer. The standard treatment for HCV is pegylated-interferon (Peg-IFN) and ribavirin (RBV), however these agents caused side effects such as bacterial infections, anemia, hematological toxicity, neutropenia and anorectal symptoms [1, 2]. Telaprevir and boceprevir were the first generation direct-acting protease inhibitors that were developed and approved for the treatment of genotype I chronic hepatitis C. However, they have to be co-administered with interferon and ribavirin therefore they were associated with their common side effects so their effectiveness were limited [3, 4]. Second-generation direct-acting antiviral drugs were developed and aimed to have a high pangenotypic activity with fewer undesirable side effects. These drugs include daclatasvir that have effective antiviral activity and genotypic coverage [5, 6].

Daclatasvir (DAC); Methyl [(2*S*)-1-[(2*S*)-2-[4-(4'-[2-[(2*S*)-1-[(2*S*)-2-[(methoxycarbonyl) amino]-3-methylbutanoyl]-2-pyrrolidinyl]-1*H*-imidazol-4-yl]-4-biphenyl)-1*H*imidazol-2-yl]-1-pyrrolidinyl]-3-methyl-1-oxo-2-butanyl] carbamate, is a nucleotide analogue NS5A polymerase inhibitor [7,8]. Only few techniques were reported for the quantitative determination of DAC including different chromatographic methods [8-12], its chiral HPLC separation on a chiral stationary phase [13], stability indicating HPLC study in bulk and formulations [7] and electrochemical detection with a chitosan modified electrode [14].

The current study aimed at developing sensitive spectrophotometric methods for the determination of Daclatasvir dihydrochloride in pure and dosage forms. These methods were based on the formation of ion-pair complexes between the drug and acid dyes such as Bromothymol blue (BTB), bromocresol green (BCG) and bromophenol blue (BPB) solutions.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

Daclatasvir hydrochloride was kindly supplied by National Organization for Drug Control and Research (NODCAR), Cairo, Egypt. Daclenza[®] tablets labeled to contain 60 mg Daclatasvir per tablet produced by Memphis Pharmaceutical Industries, Egypt.

Bromothymol blue (BTB), bromocresol green (BCG) and bromophenol blue (BPB) were obtained from Merck. Methanol, 1,2-dichloroethane, dichloromethane, dimethyl formamide, dioxane, acetone, acetonitrile and chloroform and all other solvents were of HPLC grade and were supplied from El-Nasr company, Egypt and were used directly as supplied.

Instrument

The spectrophotometric measurements were carried out using a Shimadzu (1601) UV- Visible spectrophotometer with quartz cells of 1 cm optical path length incorporated with a PC computer.

Standard stock solutions preparation

Daclatasvir solution was prepared by dissolving 25 mg of the drug salt (daclatasvir dihydrochloride) in about 1.0 mL of ethanol, then quantitatively transferred into a 50- mL measuring flask and diluted to volume with dry 1,2-dichloroethane to provide a standard 500 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ solution of the drug. Working solution of lower concentration was prepared by appropriate dilution with 1,2-dichloroethane (BCG, BTB and BPB methods).

Procedure for calibration curve

Aliquots of solutions of the drug in 1.0 mL of 1,2-dichloroethane in the concentration rang 50-600 μg (BCG and BPB methods) and 50- 700 μg (BTB method) were transferred into separate 10 mL measuring flasks. To each flask, 1.0 mL of dye ($2 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$) solution in 1,2-dichloroethane was added and mixed well, and the solution was diluted to volume with 1,2-dichloroethane. The absorbance of the resultant complexes was measured instantaneously at 420, 416 and 415 nm for BCG, BPB and BTB methods, respectively, against a reagent blank similarly prepared.

Procedure for pharmaceutical formulations

For daclatasvir tables, an accurately weighed amount of the finely powdered tablets equivalent to 25 mg of the drug salt was dissolved in 1.0 mL of ethanol and 50 mL of 1,2-dichloroethane, the mixture was agitated by an electrical shaker for about 10 min. This solution was filtered and completed to 100 mL with 1,2-dichloroethane (BCG, BTB and BPB methods). More dilute solutions were prepared whenever required and analyzed by the subsequent procedures. Nominal contents of daclatasvir tablet were calculated either from previously plotted calibration graphs or by using the regression equations.

Absorption spectra

The absorption spectra of the ion associates formed between daclatasvir (DAC) and each of BCG, BTB and BPB were recorded at 300- 500 nm against the reagent blank solution and are shown in (Fig.1). The yellow ion associates showed maximum absorbance at 420, 415 and 416 nm for DAC- BCG, DAC- BTB and DAC-BPB, respectively. The measurements were thus made at these wavelengths for bulk and tablet samples.

Figure 1: Absorption spectra of ion-pair complexes of: Dacla ($60 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) with: (a) BCG ($5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), (b) BPB ($5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$), and (c) BTB ($5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) vs. Reagent blank in 1,2-dichloroethane.

Stoichiometric relationship and stability studies

The composition of ion associates was established by Job's method of continuous variation [15]. Continuous variation method of equimolar solution was employed: a $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ standard solution of drug and $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ solution of BCG, BTB and BPB, respectively, were used. A series of solutions was prepared in which the total volume of drug and reagent was kept constant at 2 mL, diluted to this volume in 10- mL measuring flask with 1,2 dichloroethane resulting in the total molar concentration of $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$. The relation between absorbance and mole fraction of drug is represented graphically in (Fig. 2), indicating that the composition of the ion associates of Dacla with BCG, BTB and BPB was found to be 1:2. This finding was anticipated by the presence of two basic centers of tertiary amines presented in two groups of 1 H-imidazolyl of drug (as indicated in Scheme 1).

Figure 2: Continuous variation plots for ion-pair complexes of: Dacla with (a) BCG, (b) BTB and (c) BPB. Total molar concentration = $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$

Scheme 1: The possible reaction mechanism of daclatasvir ion –association with (a) BCG, (b) BTB, and (c) BPB.

Results

Effect of solvent

The type of solvent employed affects both wavelength and intensity of the maximum absorption. The effect of chloroform, dichloromethane, 1,2 dichloroethane, acetone and dioxane at a fixed wavelength is shown in (Table 1). Dichloromethane or 1,2 dichloroethane was preferred because of higher absorbance of the ion-associates formed in it and being a good solvent for the preparation of dyes.

Table 1: Effect of different solvents on the absorption intensity of reaction product of daclatasvir with BCG, BTB and BPB

Solvent	Absorbance ^a		
	BCG, $\lambda = 420$ nm	BTB, $\lambda = 415$ nm	BPB, $\lambda = 416$ nm
1,2-Dichloroethane	0.52	0.37	0.55
Dichloromethane	0.52	0.38	0.56
Chloroform	0.51	0.32	0.50
1,4-Dioxane	0.42	0.28	0.43
Acetone	0.35	0.20	0.36

^a Concentration of daclatasvir = 40 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Time of reaction = 20 min.

Effect of temperature

The effect of temperature on colored complexes was investigated by measuring the absorbance values at different temperatures. It was found that the colored complexes were stable up to 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. All subsequent studies were carried out at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Effect of time

The optimum reaction time was determined by following up the color development at ambient temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). Complete color determination was obtained after 20 min in case of all dyes and remained stable at least further one hour (Fig.3).

Figure 3: Effect of time on the absorbance of the reaction product of Dacla with (a) BCG at 420 nm, (b) BTB at 414 nm and (c) BPB at 416 nm in 1,2-dichloroethane.

Concentration of Dacla = $60 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Effect of reagent concentration

The effect of reagents was studied by measuring the absorbance of solutions containing a fixed concentration of drug (DAC) and varied amounts of the respective reagent. Maximum color intensity of the complex was achieved with 1.0 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ of all reagent solutions, although a large volume of the reagent had no pronounced effect on the absorbance of the formed ion associates (Fig.4).

Figure 4: Effect of concentration of reagent on the absorbance of ion-pair complexes of: Dacla ($70 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) with BCG (a), BTB (b) and BPB (c), respectively, in 1,2-dichloroethane.

Validation

The proposed method was validated according to ICH guidelines [16] with respect to certain parameters such as linearity, Sandell's sensitivity, limit of detection, limit of quantitation, correlation coefficient, coefficient of determination, stability constant, Gibb's free energy change, accuracy, precision, and specificity.

Discussion

Various solvents like chloroform, dichloromethane, 1,2 dichloroethane, acetone and dioxane were used to check the solubility and complex formation and also to achieve maximum sensitivity and product stability, it was found that 1,2 dichloroethane was the best solvent with regard to absorptivity and stability.

Solution of daclatasvir dihydrochloride in 1,2 dichloroethane was prepared, Absorption spectra of this solution was recorded. When this solution was mixed with BCG, BTB and BPB complexes were formed and showed maximum absorbance at 420, 415 and 416 nm for DAC- BCG, DAC- BTB and DAC-BPB, respectively.

Equimolar solutions of the drug and the reagent were mixed in various proportions and absorbance of mixtures was recorded by applying Job's method of continuous variation. This method indicated that the complex was formed in the ratio of 1:2 (D: R). The absorbance of the complex was used to calculate stability constant and Gibb's free energy. The stability constant ($\log K$) was found to be 10.16, 7.87 and 10.58 for BCG, BTB and BPB respectively, showing high stability and Gibb's free energy change for complex formation was found to be 13.95, 13.55 and 14.52 Kcal mol⁻¹ for BCG, BTB and BPB respectively, showing spontaneity of the process.

The optimum reaction time was determined by recording the absorbance of the formed complex at different time intervals. It was found that the complex was formed instantaneously at room temperature but the absorbance was steady after 20 minutes of complex formation. Hence, in order to remove time effect, all observations were made after 20 minutes of complex formation.

Various concentrations of BCG, BTB and BPB reagents were added to daclatasvir solution. The color intensity was found to increase with addition of the reagent up to 1 ml of 2×10^{-3} M and then decreases, which shows that 1 ml of 2×10^{-3} M was sufficient to complex all drug present in the medium. Therefore, this concentration was used to prepare calibration curve.

Analytical parameters

Calibration curve for daclatasvir was plotted between absorbance and concentration. A linear absorbance-concentration correlation was found to be 5.0 - 60.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, 5.0 -70.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 5.0 - 60.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with correlation coefficients 0.9999, 0.9996 and 0.9999 for BCG, BTB and BPB methods, respectively. The limit of detection and limit of quantitation were calculated in accordance with equations,

$$\text{LOD} = 3\sigma/S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10\sigma/S$$

The σ is the standard deviation of the response and S is the slope of calibration graph. The limit of detection were found to be 1.22, 1.41 and 1.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and limit of quantitation were found 4.09, 4.71 and 4.16 for BCG, BTB and BPB methods, respectively, various analytical parameters were obtained as presented in (Table 2). The value of correlation coefficient indicates good linearity for the system. Value of molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity reflect high sensitivity of the method.

Table 2: Analytical parameters for ion associates of daclatasvir with BCG, BTB and BPB

Parameters	Daclatasvir		
	BCG	BTB	BPB
λ_{max} (nm)	420	415	416
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	5.0 – 60.0	5.0 -70.0	5.0 – 60.0
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.08×10^4	0.84×10^4	1.19×10^4
Sandell sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.075	0.097	0.068
Slope of regression line (b)	0.011	0.007	0.012
Intercept of regression line (a)	0.06	0.09	0.077
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999	0.9996	0.9999
Relative standard deviation (% , n = 6)	0.45	0.33	0.50
LOD ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	1.22	1.41	1.25
LOQ ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	4.09	4.71	4.16

Precision and accuracy

To determine precision and accuracy, solutions containing three different concentrations of daclatasvir within Beer's law limits were prepared and five replicate determinations were carried out for drug under investigation (Table 3). The mean calculated relative standard deviation values (RSD) varied from 0.095- 0.42, 0.286- 1.40 and 0.10 - 0.51 % for BCG, BTB and BPB methods, respectively, indicating good repeatability of the proposed methods.

Table 3: Precision and accuracy in the determination of daclatasvir with BCG, BTB and BPB

Drug	Method	Concentration of drug ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)				Standard error ^b	Confidence limits ^c
		Taken	Found \pm SD ^a	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)		
Daclatasvir	BCG	10	9.97 \pm 0.042	99.70	0.42	0.0188	9.97 \pm 0.052
		20	19.99 \pm 0.019	99.95	0.095	0.0085	19.99 \pm 0.023
		30	29.99 \pm 0.068	99.96	0.22	0.0304	29.99 \pm 0.084
		Mean		99.87	0.245		
	BTB	10	9.98 \pm 0.140	99.80	1.40	0.063	9.98 \pm 0.17
		20	20.01 \pm 0.078	100.05	0.38	0.035	20.01 \pm 0.097
		30	29.99 \pm 0.086	99.96	0.286	0.038	29.99 \pm 0.10
		Mean		99.93	0.68		
	BPB	10	10.04 \pm 0.052	100.4	0.51	0.023	10.04 \pm 0.063
		20	19.99 \pm 0.074	99.95	0.37	0.033	19.99 \pm 0.091
		30	30.02 \pm 0.032	100.05	0.10	0.014	30.02 \pm 0.038
		Mean		100.13	0.32		

^a Mean \pm standard deviation of five determinations.

^b Standard error = SD / (N)^{1/2}.

^c Confidence limits at P = 0.05 and four degrees of freedom, t = 2.776.

Robustness and ruggedness

The robustness of the spectrophotometric method was demonstrated by the constancy of the absorption intensity with deliberated minor change in the experimental parameters such as the change in the volume of reagent (\pm 0.1 mL) and the reaction time (\pm 2 min). These minor changes that may take place during the experimental operation did not affect the absorption intensity of the reaction product (RSD \leq 1.0 %), illustrating the robustness of the method.

The ruggedness of the proposed methods was evaluated by applying the developed procedure to assay of daclatasvir using the same instrument by two different analysts under the same optimized conditions at different days. Since there was no significant difference between the results obtained for recovery \pm SD% were 99.92 \pm 0.63% and 99.89 \pm 0.76% by the two analysts, respectively, the proposed methods may be considered rugged.

Specificity

The specificity of the methods were investigated by observing any interference encountered from the common tablet excipients such as talc, lactose, glucose, sucrose, starch and magnesium stearate. These excipients did not interfere with the proposed methods, the recovery of drug ranged from 99.58 to 100.05%; this fact indicates good selectivity of the methods for determination of this drug both in raw material and in tablets.

Applications

The proposed methods were applied to the analysis of pharmaceutical formulations of daclatasvir as: Daclenza tablets by BCG, BTB and BPB methods. The results of the assay of the studied drug in pharmaceutical formulations with BCG, BTB and BPB were compared with Manufacture method (HPLC). Statistical comparison of the results of the proposed and Manufacture method was performed with regard to accuracy and precision using the Student's t- and F-tests (Table 4). At 95% confidence level, the calculated t- and F-values did not exceed the theoretical values,

indicating that there is no significant difference between the proposed methods and the reported method with regard to accuracy and precision.

Table 4: Statistical analysis of the data for Daclenza tablets using BCG, BTB and BPB methods compared with HPLC method

Pharmaceutical	Statistical Values	Methods			
		BCG	BTB	BPB	HPLC method **
Daclenza (60mg daclatasvir/ tablet)	Mean±SD(%) ^a	99.92±0.37	99.87±0.4	99.97±0.42	100.29±0.46
	N	5	5	5	5
	t ^b	1.4	1.5	1.1	
	F ^b	1.6	1.3	1.2	

^a Mean ± standard deviation of five determinations.

^bTheoretical values of t- and F-tests at $P = 0.05$ are 2.306 and 6.39, respectively.

**HPLC manufacture procedure (Memphis Pharmaceutical Industries, Cairo, Egypt) personal communication.

Recovery tests were determined by adding standard drug to the pre-analyzed mixture of drug formulation. Assay was performed at three levels of standard drug and one level of sample preparation in the level of 50 - 200 % (Table 5). Daclenza tablets assay was used to determine accuracy and precision of the proposed methods for determination of drug, the average recoveries and RSD % values were recorded in (Table 5). The results of analysis of the commercial tablets (Table 4) and the recovery study (standard additions method) of drug (Table 5) suggested that there is no interference from any excipients, which are present in Daclenza tablets.

Table 5: Accuracy of BCG, BTB and BPB methods determined by recovery of daclatasvir from Daclenza tablets (standard addition method)

Pharmaceutical	Taken ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Added ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	BCG method	BTB method	BPB method
			Recovery±RSD ^a (%)	Recovery±RSD ^a (%)	Recovery±RSD ^a (%)
Daclenza (60mg daclatasvir/ tablet)	20	10	99.93±0.16	99.87±0.23	99.86±0.19
	20	20	99.98±0.06	99.97±0.09	99.94±0.1
	20	30	100.02±0.03	99.96±0.04	99.94±0.09
	20	40	99.99±0.03	99.97±0.05	99.95±0.09
	Mean		99.98±0.07	99.94±0.1	99.92±0.11

^aMean ± relative standard deviation of five determinations.

Conclusion

The suggested methods have the advantages of being simple, accurate and sensitive and could be carried out in less equipped quality control laboratories, with good precision and accuracy. These methods utilize a single step reaction and do not need any extraction process at the color development. The three methods are sensitive and permit the determination of the drug in low concentrations. Thus, these methods can be used as alternative methods to spectrophotometric and chromatographic methods for routine determination of the cited drug in bulk powder and in pharmaceutical formulations.

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